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**Final report on project
"Living Lab - Regenerative Agriculture and Agroforestry
in the Slovak Republic"
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Content

Summary	3
Report – Main Part	5
Subject and objective of the project	5
Presentation of work steps and methods used.....	5
Results – Summary of achieved results.....	18
Discussion	19
Work with the public and publicity	20
Conclusion	23

Summary

Regenerative agriculture and agroforestry, which were the subjects of this project, are considered to be a significant innovation for the development of sustainable agriculture and agroforestry in Slovakia. We regard the dissemination of this concept in practice as one of the most important tools for addressing the impacts of climate change and biodiversity loss. Regenerative agriculture is based on practices that, unlike conventional approaches, do not damage soil or the environment. In our context, we consider agroforestry to be part of regenerative agriculture, as one of the well-applicable systems. However, in current practice, agroforestry systems are used without the application of other principles of regenerative agriculture. This constitutes the uniqueness of our implemented project, in which we created, under Slovak conditions, a unique demonstration–research Living Lab area that combines, in one place, the application of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture principles.

In Slovakia, regenerative agriculture is still little known and only a small number of farms are attempting to introduce this form of farming. For this reason, the project devoted considerable attention to the collection and sharing of information. One of the objectives was also their effective transfer into practice, supported by the development of information materials, a database of farmers applying regenerative agriculture principles, and the Living Lab. Positive examples of the use of regenerative practices were also used for demonstrations for farmers and students through field trips and education directly in the field, as an effective tool for transferring knowledge into practice.

The main objective of the implemented project was to support the broader application of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry practices in Slovakia. All project activities were focused on supporting the introduction of innovative agricultural methods that are beneficial to the environment and mitigate the negative impacts of climate change.

To achieve this main objective, in the first phase we implemented activities focused on information gathering, preparation of educational materials, and further dissemination of available professional and scientific knowledge on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture. Subsequently, we prepared a database of entities operating in Slovakia that are willing to participate, together with other farmers, students, and the professional public, in the mutual exchange of innovations, new knowledge, and examples of good practice in regenerative agriculture and agroforestry. All these activities were supported and interconnected through the establishment of a Living Lab. The creation of the Living Lab, a unique demonstration area in Slovakia, made it possible to observe the benefits of these practices directly under real conditions and to educate farmers and students in the given field. After the completion of the project, the established Living Lab is intended for long-term use as a research and demonstration site, where environmental parameters, interactions between trees, crops, and soil, and the production of woody plants and field crops will be monitored, recorded, and evaluated.

The uniqueness and innovative value of the project also lie in the combination, in one place, of the introduction of innovations into practice, education, and scientific research on regenerative agriculture and agroforestry methods. Regenerative agriculture has not yet been established as a separate subject in the curricula of the Slovak University of Agriculture, with which we also established intensive cooperation within the project, nor is it anchored in Slovak legislation. This unique pilot project therefore has significant potential in Slovakia for further use in research, education of students and farmers, and the promotion and dissemination of examples of good agricultural practice.

During the project implementation period (1 January 2024 – 31 December 2025), the project was successfully implemented in all planned objectives and activities. Project implementation was structured in the following three Specific objectives:

1. Collection, preparation, and dissemination of available professional and scientific information on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

The Ekopolis Foundation gradually collected and published professional information on the website www.prepodu.sk. The website was transformed into the “Platform for Soil.” Interested parties can find a wide range of information there in the form of videos and articles. This activity also included the publication of the book *Living Soil* on regenerative agriculture and agroforestry, as well as the production of professional and promotional videos.

The Platform also organized professional events—for example, in 2024 this included the Sustainable Agriculture Field Day at the University Agricultural Enterprise of the Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Ltd. (VPP SPU) Kolíňany, and a professional seminar combined with a field excursion on the occasion of the opening of the Living Lab, “Day for Soil,” at the Arboretum Mlyňany. In 2025, we organized a two-day study trip with excursions in Austria for experts from Slovakia. The main professional event was a large conference entitled “Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change,” involving 140 participants from various sectors of society.

2. Building a database for agroforestry and regenerative agriculture for the exchange of innovations and new knowledge

Within the above-mentioned Platform for Soil, we cooperated with key stakeholders dealing with regenerative agriculture and agroforestry: the Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, the Technical University in Zvolen, the National Forest Centre Zvolen, the National Agricultural and Food Centre, and the association Bioeconomy Cluster. Through these organizations, we expanded our contacts and knowledge about farmers, new findings, and current developments in regenerative agriculture and agroforestry. Platform members are informed through a regular newsletter, to which it is possible to subscribe and thereby also become a member of the informal Platform. The created database involved 120 stakeholders by the end of the project. Within this objective, we supported farmers through contributions for plantings and the establishment of agroforestry systems in the form of tree alleys on arable land.

3. Establishment of a Living Lab for demonstration and research in the field of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

The Living Lab is a joint project of the Institute of Forest Ecology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences and the Ekopolis Foundation as the first demonstration centre of its kind in Slovakia. The Living Lab was opened at the event “Day for Soil” on 17 October 2024, attended by representatives of ministries, state institutions, the professional public, the academic community, and farmers from Slovakia and abroad. The event included the launch of the Platform for Soil, and a demonstration of the operation of the procured no-till seeder, which carried out its first sowing on the Living Lab site on this occasion. The activities of the Living Lab do not end with this project; on the contrary, the Slovak Academy of Sciences, under whose administration it operates, plans its long-term use for continuing research and promotional purposes.

Report – Main Part

Subject and objective of the project

The main objective of the planned project was to support the broader application of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry practices in Slovakia.

To achieve this main objective, in the first phase we implemented activities focused on information gathering, preparation of educational materials, and further dissemination of available professional and scientific knowledge on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture. Subsequently, we prepared a database of entities operating in Slovakia that are willing to participate, together with other farmers, students, and the professional public, in the mutual exchange of innovations, new knowledge, and examples of good practice in regenerative agriculture and agroforestry. All these activities were supported by the establishment of a Living Lab, where agroforestry and regenerative agriculture practices are combined. Project activities aimed to promote and support the introduction of innovative agricultural methods that positively influence the environment and mitigate the negative impacts of climate change. The establishment of the Living Lab, as a unique demonstration area in Slovakia, makes it possible to observe the benefits of these practices directly under real conditions and to educate farmers and students in the given field. After the completion of the project, the established Living Lab is intended for long-term use as a research and demonstration site, where environmental parameters, interactions between trees, crops, and soil, and the production of woody plants and field crops will be monitored, recorded, and evaluated. Research activities are under the auspices of the Slovak Academy of Sciences – Arboretum Mlyňany.

The uniqueness and innovative value of the project lie in the combination, in one place, of the introduction of innovations into practice, education, and scientific research on regenerative agriculture and agroforestry methods. It is a unique pilot project in Slovakia with significant potential for further use in research, education of students and farmers, and the promotion and dissemination of examples of good agricultural practice.

Presentation of work steps and methods used

(Information below is provided in a structure according to the project's Specific Objectives. For each activity we provide what was the plan stated in the application, followed by the reporting information, how the activity was realized and what was achieved.)

Specific Objective 1: Collection, preparation and dissemination of available expert and scientific information on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

Activity 1.1 – Collection and preparation of expert information on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

Plan: This activity was designed to prepare available information on agroforestry systems with a focus on Slovak conditions in conjunction with the principles of regenerative agriculture and a comparison with the latest knowledge about this type of land management in the world. Within this activity, the project's home page (landing page) www.prepodu.sk was to be operated and filled with the obtained information. For further dissemination of knowledge in the online space, in addition to the home page,

the website www.ekopolis.sk and the existing rich social networks of the Ekopolis Foundation with a wide reach to target groups within Slovakia were to be used.

Fulfilled: Within the project and this activity, the project website www.prepodu.sk – web portal/platform (landing page) underwent a fundamental and complete reconstruction. Innovation and updates of the site have been ongoing throughout the entire duration of the project from its beginning, continue to be implemented at present, and its maintenance and supplementation will continue after the end of the project. The main menu and structure of the site consist of 5 main links: About Soil, Platform For Soil, Experiences in Slovakia, Useful Links and Contact. Currently, there are 21 videos, 6 articles, 1 document for download, and 10 descriptions of practical experiences published here, totaling 38 links in four sections and subsections:

- [Skúsenosti na Slovensku](#) (Experiences in Slovakia)
- [Užitočné odkazy](#): (Useful links)
 - [Videá](#) (Videos)
 - [Články](#) (Articles)
 - [Dokumenty na stiahnutie](#) (Documents for download)

For the dissemination of knowledge in the online space, in addition to the www.prepodu.sk portal, the www.ekopolis.sk website and the existing social networks of the Ekopolis Foundation with a wide reach to target groups within Slovakia were used within this activity. Posts about project activities were also published on a new profile dedicated to regenerative agriculture on the social networks Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn. In the given reporting period, a total of 73 posts were published on these networks.

Activity 1.2 – Creation of a publication on regenerative agriculture

Plan: In this activity the Ekopolis Foundation, in cooperation with other experts, committed to develop a comprehensive publication (at least 70 pages, A5 format) providing general information and new perspectives on regenerative agriculture, which also includes agroforestry systems. The publication is intended for farmers, agricultural students, and the professional public. The plan was to be published in printed form (100 copies) and in electronic form (PDF format) on the internet at www.prepodu.sk.

Fulfilled: The publication *Living Soil and the First Steps Towards Its Understanding and Recovery* was issued by the Ekopolis Foundation in cooperation with the association Živá záhrada, involving the experts in the field. A team of renowned authors – experts, scientists, and practitioners from the agricultural sector – participated in the publication: L. Baľáková, an expert on composting; Ľ. Marhavý, a consultant for regenerative agriculture; L. Bakay, a teacher at the Slovak University of Agriculture (SPU) in Nitra; and others. The book was published in December 2025, and its release is in accordance with the project's time schedule. In combining our planned activity with other experts, we see a significant increase in the impact of the text on both the professional and general public, as well as the utilization of synergy in publishing high-quality educational materials directly related to the topic of regenerative agriculture.

The publication was issued with a length of 86 pages, in A5 format, and in a print run of 100 copies. It consists of 3 main chapters:

- Agroforestry – the return of trees to the agricultural landscape
- Regenerative agriculture
- Practical examples of soil regeneration

Its electronic form is published on the website www.prepodu.sk, <https://prepodu.sk/uzitocne-odkazy/dokumenty-na-stiahnutie/>

Activity 1.3 - Organization of excursions and participation in professional events

Plan: Within this activity, the Ekopolis Foundation, in cooperation with Arboretum Mlyňany, planned to organize excursions in the Living Lab focused on the practical presentation of procedures applied in regenerative agriculture and agroforestry. The target group consisted of agricultural students and farmers. For students of related fields (SPU Nitra) and farmers, at least two excursions were to be realized during the school year, each with 25 participants. During the project period, a total of 4 excursions for students were to take place, each with a duration of 4 hours. Two additional 4-hour excursions were to be organized in the Living Lab for farmers. Furthermore, a two-day study trip with an excursion to regenerative agriculture in Germany was to be organized for 7-10 people. Farmers and institutions already experienced in regenerative agriculture were to be visited. Participants were to obtain important information and experience from German companies in a practical form, which could be applied within the project in Slovakia. Representatives of the Ekopolis Foundation and Arboretum Mlyňany were to participate in at least two professional events (conference, seminar, exhibition) and publish at least two articles on the given issue in professional journals for the purpose of promoting this project. The Living Lab was to be part of the Arboretum Mlyňany area, which is visited by approximately 40,000 visitors annually, and thus the Living Lab is well accessible to the general public, who could learn about the principles of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry.

Fulfilled: Within the activity, 5 excursions for students and the professional public were realized in cooperation with Arboretum Mlyňany SAV, focused on the practical presentation of procedures applied in regenerative agriculture and agroforestry, as well as 1 excursion for farmers and the professional public during the opening of the Living Lab and 1 additional excursion for farmers and experts in 2025.

- Excursion 1 for students: 13.11.2024, Janko Kráľ Gymnasium Zlaté Moravce, 25 participants
- Excursion 2 for students: 13.11.2024, Gymnasium Vráble, 25 participants
- Excursion 3 for students: 13.11.2024, Párovská Gymnasium Nitra, 5 participants
- Excursion 4 for students: 13.11.2024, Gymnasium Šurany, 28 participants
- Excursion 5 for students and teachers: 23.10.2025, SPU Nitra, 32 participants
- Excursion 1 for farmers and professional public: 17.10.2024, opening of Living Lab, 60 participants
- Excursion 2 for farmers and professional public: 24.2.2025, tour of Living Lab, 52 participants

The premises of the created Living Lab are accessible year-round within the Arboretum Mlyňany exposition for all visitors. Excursions and seminars are held here based on agreement with interested parties.

Presentations at at least two professional events (conference, seminar, exhibition) and the publication of at least two articles on the given issue in professional literature were planned. Of these, we managed to realize 1 presentation with a lecture (Martin Gálik) at the Field Day in Kolíňany and 1 lecture (Peter Ferus, Arboretum Mlyňany) within the opening of the Living Lab during the first monitoring period. We actively participated in the European Agroforestry Conference EURAF in Brno, where Martin Gálik and Peter Ferus jointly presented 1 poster (published abstract in the conference proceedings) with information about the project. In 2024 and 2025, we also actively participated in the nationwide agricultural exhibition AGROKOMPLEX. In 2024, we organized a discussion panel with 3 experts at this event, during which Martin Gálik gave a presentation.

In February 2025, we organized an international professional seminar held at Arboretum Mlyňany. In the second year of the project, we also participated in the IZPI (Institute of Knowledge-based Agriculture and Innovation) conference, the AgroBioTech SPU conference in Nitra, a workshop in Zvolen, and a workshop in Smolenice, where we participated in professional discussions on the topics of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry (Martin Gálik). We actively participated in the most important Slovak farming field event, the All-Slovak Field Days in Selice, where we exhibited and demonstrated our own Weaving seed drill in operation. At the same time, we promoted our project activities and offered sowing services. In 2025, we had a stand and our own presentation at the nationwide agricultural exhibition AGROKOMPLEX in Nitra, where we presented our Weaving seed drill and services. Within the accompanying events of this exhibition, we had our own lecture on the topic of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry (Peter Medveď, Martin Gálik). In October, Martin Gálik gave a professional lecture on the topic of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry as part of a workshop at IZPI in Nitra. The culmination of the organization of professional events was a major conference titled "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change." Nearly 140 participants attended this conference in Nitra. It included a lecture by Martin Gálik on the topic of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry and by Peter Ferus from Arboretum Mlyňany, who presented the first results from the established Living Lab.

We published an article in the professional periodical *Roľnícke noviny* titled "Agroforestry in Practice in Slovakia" (Martin Gálik) and 2 contributions (posters), which were also included in printed form in the professional publication issued within the "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" conference, titled "Dynamics of Soil Water in Winter Wheat Stands Grown in a Regenerative Agroforestry System" (Trizna, Ferus, Gálik) and "Agroforestry and Regenerative Principles in Practice" (Gálik).

In the summer of 2025, we organized a study trip with excursions in Austria for experts from Slovakia. The change of destination from Germany to Austria was consulted in advance with DBU. The Ekopolis Foundation conducted a two-day study trip to Austria for Slovak farmers, researchers, and teachers with the aim of being inspired by the experiences of Austrian farmers focused on agroforestry, organic, and regenerative agriculture. On the first day, participants visited Grand Farm in Absdorf, an organic farm that is a pioneer in vermicomposting, regenerative soil management, and agroforestry practices. The second visit took place at the farm of Lukas Hieret in Maria Anzbach, where they actively apply regenerative agriculture practices such as minimal soil disturbance, continuous soil cover, and composting. The second day was focused on agroforestry systems. We visited fields managed by Martin Steininger, who presented newly established agroforestry systems adapted to changing climatic conditions. The last visit took place at the Steindl farm in Wolkersdorf, which is a pioneer in integrating high-value woody plants into a combined system of field crops and trees in the form of so-

called alley cropping. The aim of the study trip was to provide practical knowledge about regenerative agriculture and agroforestry and to show how these methods can improve soil health, biodiversity, and farm resilience. Participants had the opportunity to connect directly with pioneering farmers in Austria and discuss challenges and solutions in sustainable agriculture.

Summary of our participation in events:

- European Agroforestry Conference EURAF in Brno, 27. - 31.5.2024
- Field Day in Kolíňany, 19.6.2024
- All-Slovak agricultural exhibition AGROKOMPLEX, 15. - 18.8.2024
- Opening of the Living Lab, 17.10.2024
- Participation in the IZPI conference, 6.5.2025
- Participation in the AgroBioTech conference, 16.5.2025
- All-Slovak Field Days in Selice with our own Weaving seed drill, 3.6.2025
- Participation in the workshop in Smolenice, 5.6.2025
- Study trip for experts from Slovakia on REGE and ALS in Austria, 10.-11.6.2025
- Participation in the workshop in Zvolen, 17.-18.6.2025
- All-Slovak agricultural exhibition AGROKOMPLEX in Nitra, 3.9.-7.9.2025
- Lecture by Martin Gálik on regenerative agriculture and agroforestry within the IZPI workshop, 22.10.2025
- Conference in Nitra with a lecture by Martin Gálik on regenerative agriculture and agroforestry, 29.10.2025

(Appendices: Att 1 - 1.Excursion Living Lab_17.10.2024_Agenda, Att 2 - Presence lists excursions, Att 3, 4 – Photos)

Activity 1.4 - Production of informative and educational videos on the importance of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

Plan: Production of 10 educational videos (length of one video 3-5 min.) for practical needs was to be carried out, published on the web information portal www.prepodu.sk. The videos were to be of a popular-educational nature. The primary target group for the videos consisted of farmers and students of agricultural universities (SPU Nitra). The videos are intended to explain basic principles in the following topics:

- Basic information and definition of regenerative agriculture
- Basic information and definition of agroforestry
- Importance of woody plants and their contribution to the environment
- Soil quality and carbon sequestration
- Mitigation of the negative impacts of climate change
- Silvoarable systems – Alley cropping
- Silvopastoral systems
- Managed grazing
- Cultivation of cover crops and catch crops
- No-till and strip-till

Fulfilled: 11 planned educational videos were filmed, processed, and published on the web information portal www.prepodu.sk, www.ekopolis.sk, and on social networks. The videos explain the basic principles of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture. The most important processed video is an 8-minute film „REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE - importance and benefits“ that combines footage from fields with animations (see also the communication section).

- 1) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „About regenerative agriculture“
 - i. The video presents the main principles of regenerative agriculture and the activities of the Ekopolis Foundation in this topic (link [Regeneratívne poľnohospodárstvo](#))
- 2) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Living Lab“
 - i. The video introduces the Living Lab project at its beginning, its establishment structure, chosen procedures, and the goals to be achieved. (link [Living Lab](#))
- 3) Video from the event Soil Day in the Mlyňany Arboretum SAV
 - i. The video was created during our "Day for Soil" event at the Mlyňany Arboretum, during which we ceremoniously opened the Living Lab and organized a professional seminar. It included an excursion to the established regenerative agroforestry system and a sowing demonstration (link [Deň Pre Pôdu](#))
- 4) Video „REGENERATIVE AGRICULTURE - importance and benefits“
 - i. Video about regenerative agriculture, its importance and advantages (link [Regeneratívne poľnohospodárstvo - význam a prínosy](#))
 - ii. The film was shot and entered into the competition at the AGROFILM 2025 Film Festival. The professional jury awarded it the Prize of the Slovak Agricultural and Food Chamber for a Slovak film. It was screened during the festival week in several cities across Slovakia.
- 5) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Farma Dangus“

In the video, the owner of the Dangus farm, Wenzel Lobkowicz, presents his method of regenerative rotational/managed grazing. He is among the first and two most significant farmers using this system of Aberdeen Angus cattle breeding in the Czech Republic and Slovakia. The video was created at our "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" Conference in October 2025, where this issue was presented (link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VVuFPrEF6U0&t>)
- 6) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Eko - Rege u Petra“
 - i. Farm owner Peter Viktorín presents his method of farming within the regenerative agriculture system on his farm. He also utilizes managed/rotational cattle grazing and grows field crops while adhering to the principles of regenerative agriculture. His farm is unique in that it operates under an organic regime while simultaneously being regenerative.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fnWUR-fqazo>
- 7) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Arborétum Mlyňany“
 - i. In this video, scientist Peter Ferus from the Slovak Academy of Sciences – Arboretum Mlyňany evaluates the first results achieved and measured in the Living Lab regenerative agroforestry system, which is part of this project. He also outlines the vision and goals for the coming years of managing this research-demonstration area.

- i. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J_WaOVbtZUw&t
- 8) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Modern Garden“
 - i. The smaller family farm Modern Garden strives for a gradual transition from conventional agriculture to a nature-friendly way of farming. Its owner, Martin Gálik, presents the procedures used in the video, such as the principles of regenerative agriculture, agroforestry systems in the form of alley cropping, organic cultivation, establishment of an edible forest (forest garden), intercropping, and the use of old varieties in linear vegetation elements on arable land.
 - ii. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0_rLvH3ck8U
- 9) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Sliepy z karavanu“ / „Caravan Hens“
 - i. In the video, the owner of the organic farm Sliepy z karavanu, s.r.o. presents his farm, which focuses on the cultivation of hazelnuts, combining this fruit with pasture breeding of hens, which together creates an agroforestry system. He explains the benefits resulting from this connection - fertilization with animal droppings, natural pest protection, or the production of quality eggs. His farm is also exceptional in that they finalize the production of BIO hazelnuts, other fruits and eggs in their own bakery.
 - ii. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gtxOhSD_HEU&t
- 10) Series FOR THE SOIL - video „Záhony Rozuma“ / „Rozum's beds“
 - i. Rozum's beds are an example of how the principles of regenerative agriculture can be used even in smaller gardens. This method of farming is named after its author, Volodimir Rozum from Ukraine. Bohuš Buday is the largest promoter of this system in Slovakia. In the video, he explains how these procedures work in his garden. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3dO9Lg3HORK>
- 11) Series FOR THE SOIL - Lecture by Ladislav Miko
 - i. In his lecture, Ladislav Miko engagingly explained the fundamental principles of soil life and highlighted the essential role of small, invisible-to-the-eye organisms. He emphasized that the quality of soil and the sustainability of food production depend on the presence, diversity, and functioning of these microscopic organisms. The lecture provided valuable insights into the complexity of soil ecosystems and their critical importance for agriculture and environmental health.
 - ii. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kx2DS2DflqY&t=5s>

Specific objective 2

Building a database for agroforestry and regenerative agriculture to exchange innovations and new knowledge

Activity 2.1 – Identifying farms with best practices in agroforestry and regenerative agriculture and including them in the database

Plan for activities 2.1 to 2.2, included creating a database featuring at least 50 institutions, expert organizations and farmers operating in Slovakia who could serve as examples of best practices for others. Through personal and online communication, the Ekopolis Foundation planned to identify the best examples of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry in Slovakia, include them in the database, and further present its content at professional events, excursions, and in the online space to other potential interested parties, whether from the ranks of farmers, researchers, or students.

For this purpose, the Ekopolis Foundation's planned to participate in several professional events, such as seminars, conferences, exhibitions, excursions, and field days, including the largest agricultural exhibition in Slovakia – AGROKOMPLEX, where direct communication with farmers from all over Slovakia is possible. In addition to this form, the Ekopolis Foundation was also to leverage its strength in electronic communication, social networks, and the online environment to identify examples of best practice and disseminate them to other farmers.

Fulfilled: Within this activity, communication, meetings, and the organization of joint events with partner organizations have taken place and are still ongoing, through which we identify and establish contact with farmers, stakeholders, and other organizations operating in Slovakia in the field of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry. These can become part of the created database and serve as examples of best practices for other farmers. The culmination of this activity is the implementation of the following point, 2.2. We used several procedures to fulfill the goal of this activity. In addition to drawing information from available literature sources, the internet, and professional periodicals, we mainly used personal visits to farms to search for best practice farms, meeting with farmers at many professional events held during the year, organized by state and non-profit institutions as well as agricultural interest associations. We ourselves actively prepared several professional events, or we co-participated in their organization in the form of excursions, exhibitions, field days, workshops, seminars, and conferences.

By the end of the project implementation, the database includes contacts for 120 stakeholders in the field of regenerative agriculture.

Activity 2.2 - Continuous development of the database of farmers with best practices and sharing of their experiences and its publication

Plan in this activity was continuous supplementation of the created database and its publication.

Fulfilled: Activity 2.2 follows up on the previous Activity 2.1. The collected information about identified best practice farms and organizations dedicated to regenerative agriculture or agroforestry, or whose activities are related to these fields, were summarized in a database, which to date has reached 120 items and is continuously being supplemented and updated. The database is published on the website www.prepodu.sk (<https://prepodu.sk/engine/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/Databaza-REGE.pdf>). Currently, and also after the end of the project, further collection of data and communication with partners and farmers will continue.

Activity 2.3 - Supporting farmers who want to adopt regenerative agriculture and agroforestry methods

Plan: In order to motivate farmers to join the created database of good practice examples, the Ekopolis Foundation planned to implement agroforestry-focused measures on three farms. For this

purpose, project funds would cover the costs of establishing agroforestry systems on selected farms, chosen based on a questionnaire survey among potential participants. For these farms, planting material and other equipment (trees, support stakes, protective nets, ties and other auxiliary materials, cover crop seeds) would be provided, along with professional supervision during implementation. Another form of motivation to implement these management practices on farms was support for farmers through free lending of the procured no-till seeder and crimping roller for demonstration purposes and testing directly on farmers' fields.

Fulfilled: At the project submission stage, we planned to materially support at least three farms for the implementation of agroforestry plantings. During the project, we successfully selected, planned, and implemented support on the land of four agricultural enterprises, where agroforestry systems were planted on arable land in the form of alleys in spring and autumn 2024 and 2025. These agricultural enterprises are:

- University Agricultural Enterprise SPU Nitra, planting in the Oponice cadastral area in spring 2024
- PPD Prašice, planting in Jacovce in autumn 2024
- ZAD Dvory nad Žitavou, planting in autumn 2024
- PD DEVIO Nové Sady, planting 2024–2025

Farms were selected from among the best agricultural enterprises in Slovakia, consistently ranked at the top in various Slovak rankings. Their success in primary agricultural production guarantees the sustainability of the plantings and serves as a credible inspiration for other farmers and agricultural enterprises.

(Att 6 – Photodocumentation from tree plantings)

Specific objective 3

Establishing a living laboratory for demonstration and research in agroforestry and regenerative agriculture

Activity 3.1 – Establishing of a living laboratory of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry in the Mlyňany Arboretum

Plan: For this activity, a location within the premises of the Mlyňany Arboretum was selected. For the purposes of the project – the creation of the Living Lab – the Arboretum was to provide an area of 5000 m², which was to be converted and further managed as an Alley Cropping agroforestry system. The alley system consists of rows of trees that divide larger agricultural areas into alternating parallel strips of narrower tree planting and wider strips of field crops. Cereals, oilseeds, legumes, clover, grasses and their mixtures, spices, medicinal plants, and garden crops can be grown on these areas. The distance between individual rows of trees was to be 8 m. On the agroforestry area created in this way, the inter-rows of woody plants were to be managed according to selected principles of regenerative agriculture – direct sowing (no-till technology – no-till seed drill and crimper roller), using cover crops and catch crops. This activity is performed by the Arboretum using its own financial resources, which are not part of the project budget.

Fulfilled: The Living Lab was established on the area provided by the Mlyňany Arboretum – Institute of Forest Ecology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAV), v.v.i., which is managed as an Alley Cropping agroforestry system. After the establishment of the planting in the first year, winter wheat

was sown in the autumn of 2024 according to the established crop rotation, across the entire area and in all inter-rows. For this purpose, the purchased machinery is already being used – the SUKOV Agrocutter 3000 crimper roller and the Weaving GD3001 G&F no-till seed drill. For the next growing season, the sowing of spring barley is planned, which will be sown in the spring of 2026. The selection of crops is dependent on the control plots located in the nearby University Agricultural Farm of the Slovak University of Agriculture in Kolíňany (VPP SPU). The selection of this partner for our project proved to be crucial, as, being a university enterprise, it can react flexibly and cooperate on a project of this type. Employees of VPP SPU and the Mlyňany Arboretum are directly involved in the management and maintenance of the plots as well as in the implementation of research activities.

(Att 7 - Photodocumentation from Living Lab , Att 8 - Photodocumentation purchased technology)

Activity 3.2 – Installation of research facilities

Plan: At the conclusion of the project, facilities for monitoring the impact of cultivation technologies on the grown crops and the environment were to be installed on the area created within the previous activity. Research equipment was to be installed in the Living Lab area and in at least one control area at another farmer's location to allow for comparison with the values measured in the Living Lab. The basic environmental parameters to be measured included microclimatic conditions (solar radiation, air and soil temperature and humidity), production parameters of individual system components (woody plants, field crops), physiological state of the components – non-destructively (SPAD index, porometry), occurrence of diseases and pests, soil carbon sequestration, and soil physics and chemistry. The entire activity was to be under the responsibility of the SAV Arboretum Mlyňany, and no financial resources were requested for this activity in the project.

Fulfilled: Prior to the sowing of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. Genius) with a Weaving GD3001M G&F no-till seed drill, which took place approximately 2 weeks after the application of herbicide – glyphosate to 6-meter wide strips of the original meadow stand between the trees, soil samples were taken from depths of 0-10 cm, 11-20 cm, and 21-30 cm to determine chemical (pH, conductivity, available nutrients, humus quality) and physical properties (particle size composition, bulk density, porosity). In addition, during the wheat growing season, we recorded the relative soil moisture in the specified topsoil layers (SM-100 sensors, Truebner GmbH, Germany; MicroLog V3A datalogger, EMS Brno, Czech Republic) and studied physiological parameters (phytomass production and water management) for individual system components (many are still subject to analysis and will be published later after their evaluation). Naturally, we were also interested in the final grain yield and its quality, which we compared with conventional management at the VPP SPU in Kolíňany. The entire activity took place under the responsibility of the Arboretum Mlyňany SAV, funded from their own resources.

Summary analysis results published and available by the end of 2025:

Tab.1 - Yield parameters

Grain yield in g per 1 according to individual sampling points in the Living Lab Mlyňany (AM) and according to sampling points on the control plot in VPP SPU Nitra in Kolíňany (KO):

AM 1A	665	KO 1	764
AM 1B	709	KO 2	822
AM 2A	388	KO 3	813
AM 2B	365	KO 4	839
AM 3A	497	KO 5	897
AM 3B	596	KO 6	844
AM 4A	344		
AM 4B	287		
AM 5A	627		
AM 5B	504		
AM 6A	347		
AM 6B	567		

Tab.2 - Production quality

According to individual sampling points in the Living Lab Mlyňany (AM) and according to sampling points on the control plot in VPP SPU Nitra in Koliňany (KO):

	Moisture %	Protein %	Wet Gluten %	Sedimentation ml	Test weight (Bulk density) kg/hl	TKW (Thousand Kernel Weight) g	TKW on dry matter basis g
AM 1 A	14	12	24	32,6	77,9	44,159	37,97674
AM 2 A	14,4	10,1	17	15,4	76,8	48,63	41,62728
AM 3 A	14,4	10,5	19,5	20,7	76,9	51,146	43,78098
AM 4 A	14	10,1	16,6	14,4	x	49,12	42,2432
AM 5 A	14,2	10,8	20,1	22,7	77,5	48,812	41,8807
AM 6 A	14,3	10,6	19,7	22	x	46,36	39,73052
KO 1	14	14	30,3	47,8	79,9	44,583	38,34138
KO 2	14	12,3	25,4	34,8	80,4	53,044	45,61784
KO 3	14	13,5	28,6	42,9	81,1	45,722	39,32092
KO 4	13,9	12,4	25,8	36,7	80,8	47,471	40,87253
KO 5	14	12,5	25,6	36	81,3	48,61	41,8046
KO 6	14,1	12,8	27,4	39,9	80,7	47,828	41,08425

Commentary on Tables 1 and 2 / interpretation:

Table 1 shows the winter wheat grain yields from the 2025 harvest. The amount of harvest is compared between samples taken from the regenerative agroforestry system in the Living lab in the Arboretum Mlyňany (samples in the first column, marked AM) and samples taken on the control plot of conventional cultivation in Koliňany (samples in the second column, marked KO). The above samples

are taken from an area of 1 m². The average of the above values of samples from the Arboretum (AM) in terms of yield per ha is 4.91 t/ha and in the case of conventional cultivation from Kolíňany (KO) the yield is 8.29 t/ha. Table 2 shows the quality parameters of grain according to individual sampling points in the Living Lab Mlyňany (AM) and on the control area in the VPP SUA Nitra in Kolíňany (KO).

The measured results show that the achieved grain yields in the regenerative agroforestry system are approximately 40% lower than in conventional cultivation. Similarly, in the case of grain quality parameters (Protein, Gluten), which are important from the food point of view, better samples from conventional cultivation come out in the first monitored year. This was influenced by targeted fertilization with industrial fertilizers, which was absent in the agroforestry-regenerative system.

It is assumed that in the coming years, the production capacity of the soil will increase thanks to the applied agroforestry-regenerative principles, which will reduce the difference in the yield per hectare compared to conventional cultivation. From an economic point of view, it is also important to emphasize that the success or failure of the new cultivation process under study will be determined by the price of inputs to both systems and the sales price of production. In the agroforestry-regenerative system, significantly lower fuel costs, lower need for mechanization and its wear, lower number of agrotechnical interventions, shorter working hours (personnel costs), lower costs of herbicides, zero costs of fertilizers and pesticides, compared to costs in a conventional environment, are expected. These lower costs compensate for lower yields, which can make this system not only more environmentally friendly, but also more economically advantageous for the farmer. We will focus on monitoring economic indicators in the coming years of the research.

Other parameters and values are being continuously monitored, processed, and analyzed, and will be gradually published in the professional press. Researchers from the Institute of Forest Ecology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAV), v.v.i. – Arboretum Mlyňany, will continue the research on this plot even after the conclusion of the project. These research activities are under the supervision of scientist Peter Ferus from the Slovak Academy of Sciences.

Partial results were also published as a contribution in the proceedings issued within the "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" Conference under the title „Soil water dynamics in winter wheat canopy grown in a regenerative agroforestry system“. It includes the project outputs obtained and processed to date:

- physical properties of the individual topsoil layers as a result of different soil tillage approach,
- chemical properties of individual topsoil layers in the Mlyňany Arboretum (MA) and SAU farm in Kolíňany (KO).

The poster concerning the research in the Living Lab Arboretum Mlyňany was presented at the international conference "Healthy Soil as a Base for Change" on October 29, 2025, in Nitra:

Soil water dynamics in winter wheat canopy grown in a regenerative agroforestry system

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Description of the practical solution for healthy soil

- experimental area established in 2021 on a meadow of the Mlyňany Arboretum, Institute of Forest Ecology SAS, planting 2-year-old seedlings of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.) with 8 x 4 m spacing
- planting of lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia* Mill.) plants in rows between black locust individuals in 2023
- in autumn 2024, sowing of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L., cv. Genius) using a no-till seeder Weaving GD3001M G&F (approx. 2 weeks after glyphosate application) in 6 m wide rows between trees, parallel cultivation of wheat using conventional methods at SAU farm in Kolíňany (pre-sowing soil preparation – subsoiling 30 cm, disking 10 cm)
- before the start of wheat cultivation – soil sampled in depths of 0-10 cm, 11-20 cm and 21-30 cm to determine chemical (pH, conductivity, available nutrients, humus quality) and physical properties (granular composition, bulk density, porosity) in an average sample from 6 repetitions
- April – June 2025 recording of relative soil moisture (SM-100 sensors, Truebner GmbH, Germany; MicroLog V3A datalogger, EMS Brno, Czechia, in the middle of the wheat canopy)

Tab. 1: Chemical properties of individual topsoil layers in the Mlyňany Arboretum (MA) and SAU farm in Kolíňany (KO). σ – conductivity, HA, FA – humic and fulvic acids.

	pH	σ (mS.m ⁻¹)	C (%)	N (%)	P (mg.kg ⁻¹)	K (mg.kg ⁻¹)	HA (g.kg ⁻¹)	FA (g.kg ⁻¹)	HA/FA
MA 0-10	7,12	12,6	2,84	0,251	97,3	466	6,52	6,11	1,07
MA 11-20	7,43	12,3	1,44	0,134	65,5	213	4,10	4,70	0,87
MA 21-30	7,53	13,3	1,01	0,100	65,1	310	2,89	4,10	0,70
KO 0-10	7,22	8,06	1,25	0,127	35,7	260	4,04	4,23	0,96
KO 11-20	6,96	7,13	1,23	0,125	31,9	215	4,29	4,03	1,06
KO 21-30	6,97	5,29	1,05	0,111	15,6	387	3,50	4,04	0,87

Tab. 2: Physical properties of the individual topsoil layers as a result of different soil tillage approach. Soil classes and types are identical (loamy, cambisol). ρ_d – reduced bulk density, indices n, k, s – non-capillary, capillary, semi-capillary.

	Granular composition				Porosity			
	sand (%)	dust (%)	clay (%)	ρ_d (g.cm ⁻³)	P (%)	P _n (%)	P _k (%)	P _s (%)
MA 0-10	14,7	53,0	32,3	1,22	52,4	10,1	39,8	2,5
MA 11-20	13,5	53,9	32,6	1,43	45,3	10,1	32,9	2,3
MA 21-30	13,3	54,9	31,8	1,50	42,6	8,4	32,4	1,8
KO 0-10	13,1	55,8	31,1	1,04	60,3	29,6	24,0	6,7
KO 11-20	17,9	51,9	30,2	1,48	43,7	8,9	32,5	2,2
KO 21-30	17,6	51,1	31,4	1,52	41,8	6,1	33,8	1,9

Conclusions and practical value for farmers

- the top layer of soil in the arboretum contained 2-3-fold more nutrients and 1.5-fold more humus than that in the SAU farm in Kolíňany
- due to tillage, the top soil layer of the SAU farm in Kolíňany had lower bulk density and higher total, non-capillary, and semi-capillary porosity; at greater depths, soil from the arboretum dominated in Pn
- relative soil moisture at individual depths after rain stabilized at a level 10-20% higher in the arboretum than in the SAU farm in Kolíňany
- we consider the main reason for these results to be the regenerative approach to soil management – more humus, permanent rooting, non-competitive plant understorey in wheat (the trees did not completely shade the crop, yet)

This poster was presented at the international conference 'Healthy soil as a base for change' held on 29th Oct 2025 in Nitra. The event organisers were Bioeconomy Cluster and Ekopolis Foundation.

Bioeconomy Cluster

Funded by the European Union

Management - joint activity for specific objectives 1-3

Management: Project management was performed by the Ekopolis Foundation, which, through leadership and active communication with involved partner organizations, professional organizations, the ministry, schools, farmers, advisors, suppliers, and other institutions, created suitable conditions for the implementation and achievement of all specific project objectives.

Results – Summary of achieved results

Activity – Title	Planned Implementation Period	Achieved Results / Comment
Activity 1.1 – Collection and preparation of expert information on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture	1/2024 - 3/2025	Implemented continuously; Information published on www.prepodu.sk and www.ekopolis.sk
Activity 1.2 – Creation of a publication on regenerative agriculture	1/2025 - 12/2025	Implemented in the second year of the project. Publication issued in A5 format, with 86 pages and a print run of 100 copies ²
Activity 1.3 – Organization of excursions and participation in professional events	4/2024 - 10/2025; 10/2024 - 2/2025; 5/2024 – 10/2025; 2024-2025	5 excursions for students, 2 excursions for farmers and the professional public. ³ Active participation in 13 professional events, including the organization of 4 own events, 1 foreign study trip to Austria, 4 contributions in professional publications ⁴
Activity 1.4 – Production of informational and educational videos on the importance of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture	3/2024 - 11/2024; 3/2025 - 11/2025	Production of the first 4 videos implemented in the first year. 6 videos were produced in the second year. All 10 videos published on the website www.prepodu.sk
Activity 2.1 – Identifying farms with best practices in agroforestry and regenerative agriculture and including them in the database	1/2024 - 12/2025	Implemented continuously throughout the project duration - farms are identified and this activity continues in the following Activity 2.2
Activity 2.2 – Publication and continuous supplementation of the database of farmers with best practices and sharing of their experiences	1/2025 - 12/2025	Continuation of Activity 2.1 and publication of the created database on the website www.prepodu.sk

Activity 2.3 – Support for farmers who want to adopt regenerative agriculture and agroforestry methods	3/2024 - 4/2024; 3/2025 - 4/2025	Completely implemented; 4 farms supported – support for planting woody plants in an agroforestry system
Activity 3.1 – Establishing of a living laboratory of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry in the Mlyňany Arboretum	3/2024 - 12/2025	Living Lab established, machinery purchased – No-till seed drill Weaving GD 3001M G&F and cutting roller SUKOV 3000
Activity 3.2 – Installation of research facilities	3/2024 - 6/2024; 3/2024 – 12/2025	Research facilities installed. Following installation, monitoring of microclimatic conditions, continuous measurement and taking of soil samples, their analysis and evaluation. Publication of results at the "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" conference in Nitra and through contributions in professional literature.
Management – Joint activity for specific objectives 1-3	1/2024 - 1/2025	Implemented continuously

Discussion

To what extent were the objectives achieved with regard to the original goal?

The established objectives, as presented in the application, were fulfilled within the project implementation in the years 2024 and 2025. An overview of the fulfillment of objectives is processed in the table above. Given the nature of the topic and the research focus, research activities will continue to be carried out.

Deviations from Planned Project Objectives

(Arisen problems, changes in strategy or used methods)

No fundamental deviations or problems occurred during the project implementation. On the contrary, the project and the chosen strategy worked very well – we are achieving the planned practical results, and most importantly, it is valuable that both the professional environment and practical farmers perceive and appreciate our activities very positively.

Nevertheless, minor changes did occur and resulted from practical reasons. Compared to the original plan, we were forced to adjust the crop rotation of field crops in the Living Lab at the Mlyňany Arboretum. In each of the inter-rows of the agroforestry system, we grew the same single crop in a given year, with winter wheat being the crop in the first year. Establishing an agreement with a local farmer who would sow the same crops on their plots under conventional agriculture proved to be difficult; such an agreement was necessary to allow for measurement, sampling, evaluation, and comparison with our plots in the Living Lab as a control. This agreement was eventually concluded with the nearby University Agricultural Farm of the Slovak University of Agriculture Nitra in Kolíňany. In addition to using the same crop, the same machinery – the Weaving GD 3001M seed drill – was also

used. Given that a different crop rotation is planned long-term for this conventionally used plot, we were forced to adapt ours to ensure mutual compatibility. On the other hand, this agreement and change also had a significant positive effect in that we could share the professional background and personnel of the SUA Nitra with the Mlyňany Arboretum and the Ekopolis Foundation within our project, as well as establish good relations that promise successful cooperation in the future.

Functioning of cooperation with various partners (Institutions, companies, municipalities, associations, etc.)

Within the project and its thematic focus, we established new partnerships and cooperation with several organizations. Specifically, these include: Institute of Forest Ecology – SAS, Arboretum Mlyňany; Slovak University of Agriculture (SPU) Nitra; University Agricultural Farm SPU, s.r.o. (VPP SUA); Technical University in Zvolen (TUZVO); Bioeconomy Cluster; National Forest Centre (NLC); National Agricultural and Food Centre (NPPC); Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic; Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic; Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber (SPPK); Ekotrend; Slovak Agroforestry Association (SAA); Bioprutex, s.r.o.; Slovak Association for Regenerative Agriculture; Slovak Union of Agrobusinessmen and Family Farms (SZARF); BISO Schrattenecker, s.r.o.; Nestlé Slovakia; Plzeňský Prazdroj and others.

The most intensive cooperation took place with the Arboretum Mlyňany SAS, VPP SPU Nitra, and the Bioeconomy Cluster. Together with these partners, we co-organized our most important events of the year, such as the AGROKOMPLEX exhibition in Nitra, the Field Day in Kolíňany, the Soil Day at the Arboretum Mlyňany, and the "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" conference in Nitra. We invited representatives of the SPPK (the largest self-governing agricultural organization in Slovakia), the Ministry of Agriculture, and SPU Nitra as speakers to our professional events. Our goals and visions overlap with these strategic partners in many aspects; therefore, we anticipate that successful cooperation will continue in the future.

Work with the public and publicity

In general, it was promoted in several ways, through information on websites, social networks and during events. The central communication channel of the project is the website www.prepodu.sk.

An important project milestone was the opening of the Living Lab, which we also used for communication purposes. The event resulted in several short documents, and on this occasion we also created a comprehensive document "Regenerative agriculture - meaning and benefits", which presents the concept of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry to the wider public. Until now, a similar document was not available for the audience in Slovakia:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KWPB6kI2gwQ>.

This film was awarded the Prize of Slovak Chamber of Agriculture and Food Award for Slovak film at the specialized film festival AGROFILM 2025 (www.agrofilm.sk).

Summary of communication activities and outcomes in year 2024

Information on the websites:

- On the website of the Ekopolis Foundation - <https://ekopolis.sk/zivotne-prostredie/living-lab>, <https://ekopolis.sk/2024/na-slovensku-vznikne-unikatny-living-lab>, <https://ekopolis.sk/2024/v-kolinanoch-sa-uskutocnil-polny-den-udrzatelneho-polnohospodarstva>, <https://ekopolis.sk/2024/agrokomplex-2024-osveta-a-spolupraca-v-regenerativnom-polnohospodarstve>, <https://ekopolis.sk/2024/v-arborete-mlynany-sa-stretli-odbornici-na-temu-regenerativneho-polnohospodarstva>
- On the website www.prepodu.sk, dedicated to regenerative agriculture - <https://prepodu.sk/na-slovensku-vznika-unikatny-living-lab/>, <https://prepodu.sk/agrolesnicka-konferencia-euraf-v-brne/>, <https://prepodu.sk/v-kolinanoch-sa-uskutocnil-odborny-seminar-a-exkurzia/>, <https://prepodu.sk/agrokomplex-2024-osveta-a-spolupraca-v-regenerativnom-polnohospodarstve/>, <https://prepodu.sk/v-oktobri-sa-uskutocni-den-pre-podu/>, <https://prepodu.sk/v-arborete-mlynany-sa-stretli-odbornici-na-temu-regenerativneho-polnohospodarstva/>, <https://prepodu.sk/ekopolis-ponuka-farmarom-pomocnu-ruku-v-oblasti-regenerativneho-polnohospodarstva/>

Number of published posts and articles: 12

Social networks:

- Posts about project activities on the profile of the Ekopolis Foundation on the social network Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/nadacia.ekopolis>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/nadaciaekopolis/>) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nadacia-ekopolis>)
- Posts about project activities on the new profile dedicated to regenerative agriculture on the Facebook social network (<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61568605514364>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/prepodu.sk/>) a LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/pre-podu>)

Number of published posts: 30

Youtube channel of Ekopolis Foundation – 4 videos

- Series FOR THE SOIL - video about principles [Regeneratívneho poľnohospodárstva](#)
- Series FOR THE SOIL - video about the project [Living Lab](#)
- video from the event [Deň Pre Pôdu](#)
- video [Regeneratívne poľnohospodárstvo - význam a prínosy](#)

In the first monitoring period, we organized and participated in several events where we presented the given project to the professional and general public:

- On **June 19, 2024**, the University Agricultural Enterprise of the Slovak University of Agricultural Sciences, s.r.o. – Kolíňany held a Field Day of Sustainable Agriculture. The event was attended by representatives of the university, the professional public and representatives of farmers. You can find more information about the event at <https://prepodu.sk/v-kolinanoch-sa-uskutocnil-odborny-seminar-a-exkurzia/>
- On **August 15-18, 2024**, the Ekopolis Foundation actively participated in the Agrokomplex exhibition for the second time. In addition to the many talks, education and advice that we provided at our stand, we also organized a discussion panel on the topic "How and why to plant trees in agricultural land?". You can find more information at <https://prepodu.sk/agrokomplex-2024-osveta-a-spolupraca-v-regenerativnom-polnohospodarstve/>
- On **October 17, 2024**, Day for Soil was held in the Mlyňany Arboretum. The event was attended by representatives of ministries, state institutions, the professional public, the academic community, farmers from Slovakia and abroad. The event included professional lectures, an excursion to the Living Lab and the launch of a no-till seeder. You can find more

information at <https://prepodu.sk/v-arborete-mlynany-sa-stretli-odbornici-na-temu-regenerativneho-polnohospodarstva/>

From the events, we prepared 3 press releases for the national media, in which we reported on the outcomes of the events. In 2024, our press monitoring in connection with the project recorded 28 media outputs in national media.

Summary of communication activities and outcomes in year 2025

Newsletters and Online Information: During the year, we sent 5 newsletters to 181 subscribers representing the public and private sectors, educational institutions, and farmers.

Information on websites:

- On the Ekopolis Foundation website (<https://ekopolis.sk/zivotne-prostredie/living-lab>).
- On the www.prepodu.sk website dedicated to regenerative agriculture, managed by the Ekopolis Foundation (<https://prepodu.sk/konferencia-o-zdravej-pode-ukazala-potrebu-spoluprace-napriec-sektormi>).

Information on social media:

- **24 posts** about activities on the Ekopolis Foundation profiles - Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/nadacia.ekopolis>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/nadaciaekopolis/>), and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nadacia-ekopolis>)
- **80 posts** about activities on the dedicated regenerative agriculture profiles (**Pre pôdu**) on Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61568605514364>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/prepodu.sk/>), and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/pre-podu>)

Events and Presentations: During 2025, we organized and participated in several events to present the project to both professional and general audiences:

- Participated in the conference "CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027: How new financial instruments and sustainable soil management practices will shape the future of Slovak agriculture" (May 6, 2025, Nitra); the international roundtable "Regenerative agriculture and plant production under changing environmental conditions" (May 16, 2025, Nitra); and the meeting of members of the National Network for Biodiversity-friendly Agriculture within the FarmBioNet program (June 5). Participated in the professional workshop "Agroforestry in Slovakia, examples from practice" combined with a field excursion to Vrchdetva (June 17–18, 2025).
- We participated in the All-Slovak Field Days in Selice (June 3–4, 2025), where we presented the WEAVING GD3001M seed drill with the SUKOV AGROCUTTER 3000 cutting roller.
- In June, we organized a two-day study trip to Austria for Slovak farmers, researchers, and educators to be inspired by the experiences of Austrian farmers focused on agroforestry, organic, and regenerative agriculture.
- At the 50th anniversary of the Agrokomplex exhibition (September 3–7, 2025), we exhibited the Weaving GD 3001M G&F no-till seed drill. Peter Medved' and Martin Gálík delivered a lecture on agroforestry and regenerative agriculture within the professional program.

- "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" Conference: On October 29, 2025, we co-organized this international conference in Nitra with the Bioeconomy Cluster, attracting 140 participants.
- Excursions in Living Lab: In February 2025, we organized an excursion for 46 students and experts. In October, the Living Lab was visited by 32 students from SUA Nitra.

Following the events, we issued press releases to national media. Our media monitoring recorded 20 media outputs in national media outlets related to the project in 2025.

The 4 videos from 2024 were supplemented by the production of an additional 7 videos:

4 of those on the topic of practical experiences in regenerative agriculture:

- Practical Experience: Eko – Rege at Peter's (<https://youtu.be/fnWUR-fqazo>).
- Practical Experience: Rozum's Beds (<https://youtu.be/3dO9Lg3HORK>).
- Practical Experience: Caravan Hens (https://youtu.be/gtxOhSD_HEU).
- Practical Experience: Modern Garden (https://youtu.be/0_rLvH3ck8U)

Summary of results after the 1st growing season in the Living Lab (https://youtu.be/J_WaOVbtZUw)

2 expert presentations from the "Healthy Soil as the Basis for Change" conference processed into videos:

- Presentation of Farm Dangus (<https://youtu.be/VVuFPrEF6U0>)
- Presentation by Ladislav Miko (<https://youtu.be/qEfUKPyvCx8>).

Who participates in the results?

The target group for which the project outputs are intended primarily includes farmers, agricultural students, researchers, and the professional public. Through the living laboratory, excursions, a specialized portal, a database, educational materials, and specialized agricultural machinery, we aim to provide farmers with the necessary information, give them the opportunity to test innovative procedures, and help them put these into practice. The project is primarily focused on small and medium-sized farms, which are more willing to implement similar ecologically oriented innovations. We provide scientists, experts, and students of agricultural and natural sciences with opportunities to engage in research and professional activities. The published book "Living Soil" is intended for the general public, including laypeople, and is aimed at explaining the principles of agroforestry and regenerative agriculture and their popularization in Slovak society.

Conclusion

Has the chosen procedure proven itself or have the project methods changed?

Upon the conclusion of the project, we specifically evaluate as highly positive our decision to choose the Arboretum Mlyňany SAS as a strategic partner; they provided not only the experimental plot for the Living Lab but also other facilities and, most importantly, their professional expertise. The same applies to the University Agricultural Farm SUA, s.r.o. (VPP SUA), which significantly assists us in the practical implementation of activities, particularly regarding the handling, storage, and operation of

the purchased specialized machinery. This enterprise also offered its facilities for establishing parallel experiments under conventional management. Both organizations were remarkably helpful in organizing professional events directly on their premises. Together with our partner, the Bioeconomy Cluster, which possesses strong expertise in Slovak and EU agricultural policy, we have created the foundation of a platform that can significantly advance the topics of regenerative agriculture and agroforestry in Slovakia.

Were changes necessary to achieve the project goals?

To achieve the goals set during the project submission, it was not necessary to make any major changes during its implementation. The established objectives were successfully fulfilled through the procedures and activities defined in the specific goals, with the exception of the change in crop rotation, as stated and justified above.

Appendices

We present the list of attachments - photos sorted by Activities to which they belong, with the name of the activity, date and author - in a separate attachment.